

DiSSCo related output

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Title

D7.2 Draft Statutes and future milestones for the creation of DiSSCo ERIC

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Abstract

After a thorough analysis of the various models suitable for establishing the DiSSCo RI as a legal entity, the conclusion arose that the most adequate model was the European Research Infrastructure Consortium ("ERIC").

The Statutes of several well established ERICs were compared and an initial draft of the Statutes was set up in order to feed the consultation of various groups of stakeholders: the partners of the task, the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office, the DiSSCo National Nodes, and the country representatives participating to the Funders Forum. Several iterations lead to substantial improvements, reflecting what the DiSSCo community wants to do and how it will formally organize its activities and functioning to achieve the objectives.

The current Deliverable presents the latest version to date of the draft Statutes of DiSSCo ERIC (December 2022) and the process that lead to it.

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DiSSCo Prepare WP7 – Draft Statutes and by-laws; Implementation plan

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The Statutes of several well established ERICs were compared and an initial draft of the Statutes was set up in order to feed the consultation of various groups of stakeholders: the partners of the task, the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office, the DiSSCo National Nodes, and the country representatives participating to the Funders Forum. Several iterations lead to substantial improvements, reflecting what the DiSSCo community wants to do and how it will formally organize its activities and functioning to achieve the objectives.

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Contribution to DiSSCo RI (FOR DELIVERABLES ONLY)

The present report delivers a very advanced version of the cornerstone of the governance of DiSSCo RI when established as a legal entity: its Statutes.

This document is now (December 2022) handed over to the Funders Forum for further discussion and refinement in close collaboration with the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office

Keywords

European Research Infrastructure Consortium, ERIC, Legal Entity, Statutes

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01 Background: choice of the legal entity model

The most important reason for establishing an RI as a legal entity is to provide an instrument to ensure its sustainability in the long term. In order to select the most suitable model, the partners:

1. identified the criteria and characteristics of the DiSSCo objectives and governance.
2. screened other RIs from the same Environment Domain, with the same distributed type and entered on the 2018 Roadmap. But also obtained experiences from other RIs belonging to other domains that have chosen to become a legal entity.
3. obtained the support of a legal advisor to go deeper in the legal assets of each entity model available for DiSSCo.

The following six legal entity models

- International/Intergovernmental Organisation (IO)
- European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)
- European Economic Interest Grouping (EEIG)
- European Groupings of Territorial Cooperation (EGTC)
- Belgian AISBL
- Dutch Stichting

were screened according to 15 points of attention:

1. Is it a separate legal entity?
2. Does it have the capacity to contract with third parties, hire personnel, open a bank account, buy equipment, sue and be sued, *etc.*?
3. Can institutions from EU/EEA Member States be members?
4. Can institutions from non-EU/EEA Member States be members?
5. Can EU/EEA governments (ministries) be members?
6. Can non-EU government (ministries) be members?
7. Is the establishment process simple and fast?
8. Is the legal entity exempted from the EU public procurement directives (Art. 9(1)(b) Directive 2014/24/EU)?
9. Is the legal entity exempted from VAT (in the sense of Articles 143(1)(g) and 151(1)(b) of the VAT Directive)?
10. Is the legal entity able to carry out economic activities?
11. No initial capital requirements.
12. Is there a limited liability regime (legal entity, governing body and for members)?
13. Is the governance structure flexible?
14. Is the legal entity able to receive EU and national grants?
15. Is the legal entity able to contract bank loans?

Thanks to this first screening, three models were shortlisted: International organization, ERIC and the Belgian AISBL. As International Organizations present more or less the same pros and cons than ERICs but at the price of a much heavier establishment process, the actual final choice was to make between ERIC and AISBL.

The final round, based on specific practical criteria:

	AISBL	ERIC
Level of integration between the <u>DiSSCo</u> legal entity and the national nodes	+	++
Location of the statutory seat	+	++
Language to be used for the official documents	+	++
Membership	Institutions, individuals	Countries, IOs
Participation by CETAF	++	+
“Branding” and network possibilities	+	++
Procurement and VAT considerations	+/-	++
Tailor-made governance structure	+	++
Securing funding	+/-	++

lead to the conclusion that the ERIC legal entity model was the most suitable for establishing DiSSCo RI as a sustainable organization.

02 Drafting of the DiSSCo Statutes, methodology

Principles for drafting

At the beginning of the work of the SWG, the key principles underlying the approach to the Statutes were discussed and agreed:

- **Hierarchy of documents:** In addition to the statutes, there will be Implementing Rules, which will include the internal rules and procedures detailing the organisation and work of the DiSSCo-ERIC bodies. Various policies, guidelines and contracts will be adopted, addressing in greater detail certain aspects mentioned in the statutes. Examples of the policies include the procurement policy/rules, data policy, IPR policy, access policy, etc.

- **Correct allocation:** The documents mentioned above are in a descending order of authority, whereby the Statutes having the greatest authority and as such they should only address the main principles, structure and norms of the DiSSCo-ERIC. The SWG will give due consideration to allocating the ideas, thoughts and principles they wish to address and to allocate them to the correct category within the document hierarchy
- **Simplicity:** It is desirable that the statutes will be drafted in a plain and simple manner, so as to avoid ambiguity and differing understandings of the text. It is likely that the content of discussion within the drafting team will not pass on as a tool of interpretation if the Statutes later in time and there will be no separate guidance on what exactly was meant by the drafting team. Therefore, it is important that the Statutes is simple and clear so there is not more than one way to understand the purpose and content of each Article in the Statutes.
- **Flexibility:** For similar reasons, the Statutes need to allow a degree of flexibility for changing circumstances and avoid being over-descriptive.
- **Best practice:** When drafting the statutes, it is important to look at other ERICs and to assess what works well in their Statutes and what does not work well. Over the years, many provisions in the statutes of new ERICs have been more or less standardised, and there is no need to invent the wheel each time.
- **Tailor the rules to DiSSCo-ERIC's needs:** At the same time, simple 'copy paste' from other ERICs may be counterproductive and it is therefore important to assess each article separately and adjust it in accordance with the tasks, objectives and the proposed governance structure of DiSSCo-ERIC.
- **Drafting:** It needs to be done by those 'skilled in the art' of drafting legal documents in order to make sure that the oral discussions and understandings of the drafting group is 'translated' correctly into the legal text. Coherent, structured and legally correct drafting is crucial to producing high quality Statutes.
- **Reasonable expectations:** Given that the intention for DiSSCo-ERIC is that it will last for many years, it is unlikely that anyone at this point of time will be able to predict with great detail how things will develop in the future and therefore, in accordance with the principles of simplicity and flexibility, the expectations from the final version of the Statutes should be reasonable, so as to cover the basic elements and structure of the DiSSCo-ERIC but without going beyond this.

Consecutive steps

First, a synoptic table of the Articles of the Statutes of well-established ERICs has been prepared.

These RIs were:

- e-RIHS,
- DARIAH,
- BBMRI,
- EPOS, and
- ICOS.

Then, with the principles listed above and the Governance Model for DiSSCo in mind, a first version of possible Statutes for DiSSCo ERIC was drafted and discussed amongst the Partners of the Task 7.2.

This methodology and the next steps were presented during the 4th Funders Forum meeting (16–17 June 2022). In that meeting, the Funders Forum members decided to create an *ad hoc* writing group

with the direct participation of four national representatives (Netherlands, Italy, France and Belgium), the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office, a legal advisor and key partners of Task 7.2.

The Statutes Writing Group (SWG) met regularly for three months and prepared an advanced draft of the statutes.

This document was submitted for comments to the DiSSCo National Nodes in early October 2022. The results of this consultation process were synthesized in a note that was part, together with the advanced draft Statutes, of the meeting documents of the 5th Funders forum meeting.

03 Current status of the by laws

At the time of writing the DiSSCo Prepare proposal, we were a bit too optimistic about the pace of the project. We underestimated the time needed for the consultation and for the coordination of the various advisory bodies (project partners, CSO, National Nodes, Funders Forum).

The by-laws are not yet in a sufficiently mature version to be presented here. Nevertheless, some fundamental documents for the set-up of DiSSCo ERIC are very well advanced:

- the Governance Model,
- the Cost Book and the proposal for calculating the National contribution,
- the Technical and Scientific description.

The CSO and some of the key actors of the DiSSCo community have already committed themselves to keep working on this portfolio of funding documents in the coming months.

04 Next steps concerning the Statutes and the establishment of DiSSCo ERIC

The future of the Statutes now resides largely in the hands of the country representatives.

The discussion started at the 5th Funders Forum meeting. Its members agreed to provide high-level recommendations on the text to be included in the version of the Statutes and annexes (incl. financial provisions), that will be part of the negotiations among the Host and Founding members of DiSSCo ERIC. If necessary, the Funders Forum will include this topic in the agenda for the next meeting).

The draft Statutes and annexes will be part of the agenda of the 6th DiSSCo interim General Assembly (February 9-10, 2023). Following the discussions in that meeting, the draft Statutes will be handed over to the representatives of the Host country and Founding members for agreement.

The call for Host and Founding members will be launched during the Q2 of 2023 and will lead to the preparation of ERIC Step 1 during the second half of the year.

Submission of Step 1 of the ERIC application process is foreseen to take place early in early.

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- 05 Annex: current draft of DiSSCo ERIC Statutes, as presented to the 5th Funders Forum meeting, 14–15 December 2022

**Statutes of the Distributed System of Scientific
Collections - European Research Infrastructure
Consortium
(DiSSCo ERIC)**

DRAFT

Version 3.0

13 October 2022

PREAMBLE

[List of Member countries and Internationals]

Hereinafter referred to as 'the Members',

and:

[List of Observer countries and International Organisations]

Hereinafter referred to as 'the Observers'.

[to be completed]

HAVE AGREED AS FOLLOWS:

CHAPTER 1 – ESSENTIAL ELEMENTS

Article 1

Name and statutory seat

1. There shall be a European distributed research infrastructure called the “Distributed System of Scientific Collections”, hereinafter referred to as ‘DiSSCo’.
2. DiSSCo shall have the legal form of a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) under Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 and be named ‘DiSSCo ERIC’.
3. DiSSCo ERIC shall have its statutory seat in [INSERT NAME OF COUNTRY].

Article 2

Task and activities

1. The principal task of DiSSCo ERIC is to establish and operate the DiSSCo research infrastructure and to coordinate the work required to achieve the strategic objectives of DiSSCo.
2. To this end, DiSSCo ERIC shall undertake or coordinate the following activities:
 - a) Facilitate and promote the digital transformation of Natural Science Collections in Europe and globally;
 - b) Promote natural science collections and the collections-to-impact value chains by investing in mobilisation of open and FAIR data;
 - c) Co-develop strategic and operational frameworks in which Natural Science Collections can deliver impact in accordance to their mission;
 - d) Develop (digital) services and resources that improve the adoption of Natural Science Collections-derived evidence in science, policy and society;
 - e) Lower the access barriers faced by users and researchers to collections;
 - f) Provide a central integrated access point to partner facilities and their resources;
 - g) Support and coordinate a community of distributed Nodes;
 - h) Support the advancement of the scientific understanding of natural science collections and in this way contribute to their long-term preservation;
 - i) Promote a culture of cross-disciplinary and trans-national collaboration through supporting researchers in developing comprehensive, advanced scientific and technological expertise, including training;
 - j) Seek innovative collaborations with actors outside of the immediate landscape of Natural Science Collections, in order to further expand the reach of Collections;
3. In addition, DiSSCo ERIC may carry out the following activities:

- a) Seek to facilitate the mobility of researchers and Users;
 - b) Identify European projects of interest to natural history collections and related funding opportunities, and to guide interested partners in their applications;
 - c) Establish international partnerships with other European and non-European organisations in natural science collections and related fields;
 - d) Carry out any other activity necessary to fulfil its task.
4. DiSSCo ERIC shall pursue all of its activities ethically and transparently, and shall avoid potential organisational or personal conflicts of interest.
 5. DiSSCo ERIC shall pursue its main task on a non-economic basis, however it may carry out limited economic activities, provided that they are closely related to its main task and that they do not jeopardise the achievement thereof. Any income generated by these limited economic activities shall be used by DiSSCo ERIC to further support its main task and activities.

Article 3

Duration and winding up

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall exist for an indefinite period of time.
2. The winding up of the DiSSCo ERIC shall require a decision of the General Assembly in accordance with Article 21(9)(b).
3. Without undue delay and in any event within ten days of the winding up decision, DiSSCo ERIC shall notify the European Commission of its decision.
4. Assets remaining after payment of DiSSCo ERIC debts shall be apportioned among the Members in proportion to their annual accumulated contributions to DiSSCo ERIC over the last five consecutive years prior to the year of winding up.
5. Within ten days after the closure of the winding-up procedure, DiSSCo ERIC shall notify the European Commission thereof.
6. The DiSSCo ERIC shall cease to exist on the day on which the European Commission publishes the appropriate notice in the Official Journal of the European Union.

Article 4

Liability and insurance

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall be liable for its debts.
2. The members shall not be jointly liable for the debts of DiSSCo ERIC.

3. The financial liability of the Members for DiSSCo ERIC's debts shall be limited to their respective annual contribution to DiSSCo ERIC calculated on the basis of the last full year of operation.
4. DiSSCo ERIC shall take appropriate insurance to cover the risks specific to its activities.

Article 5

Scientific evaluation

1. The activities of DiSSCo ERIC shall be evaluated every five years by an independent panel, composed of international experts of the highest quality, appointed by the General Assembly.
2. The expert panel shall evaluate DiSSCo ERIC activities, scientific and strategic orientation as well as the operation of the research infrastructure. Special attention shall be given to the fulfilment of User requirements.
3. The results of the evaluations shall be reported to the General Assembly.

Article 6

Access policy for users

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall maintain fair and transparent procedures to provide Users access to DiSSCo's facilities, data and services.
2. As a general rule, access to the DiSSCo ERIC facilities, data and services shall be based on open access principles and collaborative research practices, but may be subject to a fee-based policy.
3. DiSSCo ERIC shall adopt an access policy for Users, for approval by the General Assembly.

Article 7

Dissemination policy

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall be a facilitator of research and shall as a general rule encourage as free access as possible to research data.
2. DiSSCo ERIC shall encourage Users to make their research results publicly available or publish in peer-reviewed scientific literature, to present them at scientific conferences and make their results available through DiSSCo ERIC.

3. DiSSCo ERIC shall use the most appropriate and far-reaching channels to reach its target audiences, including web portal, newsletter, workshops, presence in conferences and events, articles in magazines and journals, social media, newspapers and other channels as may be appropriate.

Article 8

Intellectual property rights policy

1. Subject to any contract between DiSSCo ERIC and a third party, intellectual property rights created, obtained or developed by a third party shall be owned by the third party.
2. Subject to any contract between DiSSCo ERIC and a third party, intellectual property rights created, obtained or developed by DiSSCo ERIC shall be owned by DiSSCo ERIC.
3. DiSSCo ERIC shall adopt a policy on intellectual property rights for approval by the General Assembly.

Article 9

Employment policy

1. DiSSCo ERIC employment policy shall be governed by the laws of the country in which staff is employed or in the country where they work, as may be determined by applicable law.
2. Vacant positions at DiSSCo ERIC shall follow a transparent, non-discriminatory procedure and respect the principles of equal opportunity, subject to applicable labour laws.

Article 10

Procurement policy

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall adopt its own procurement rules, to be approved by the General Assembly.
2. The procurement rules shall respect the principles of transparency, non-discrimination and competition.

CHAPTER 2 – GENERAL PROVISIONS

Article 11

Definitions

For purposes of these Statutes, the following defined terms and expressions shall have the following meaning:

Calendar year means the period starting the 1st of January and ending on the 31st of December of each year.

National Node is a legal entity or a structure appointed by a Member, which is in charge of

organising the national provision of data and services (or both) to DiSSCo ERIC or to Users on behalf of DiSSCo ERIC.

Days means calendar days, unless otherwise indicated.

Coordination and Support Office (CSO) means the central office of DiSSCo ERIC, located in the Statutory Seat.

Implementing Rules means the internal rules and procedures detailing the organisation and work of the DiSSCo ERIC bodies.

Intellectual Property shall have the same meaning as Article 2 of the Convention Establishing the World Intellectual Property Organisation signed on 14 July 1967.

Service Level Agreement (SLA) means an agreement between an entity and DiSSCo ERIC that regulates the provision of services, data, facilities or resources to DiSSCo ERIC or to Users on behalf of DiSSCo ERIC.

Service Provider Node: an entity that has concluded an SLA with the DiSSCo ERIC.

Users means individuals and organisations from academia, business, industry and public services that are granted access to the DiSSCo facilities, data and services.

Representing Organisation of the National Node (RONN) means a legal entity appointed by a National Node which is authorised to represent the National Node before the DiSSCo ERIC and to conclude an SLA with DiSSCo ERIC on behalf of the National Node.

Article 12

Working language

The working language of DiSSCo ERIC shall be English.

Article 13

Statutes updates and availability

The Statutes shall be kept up to date and made publicly available on the DiSSCo ERIC website and at the statutory seat.

CHAPTER 3 - MEMBERSHIP

Article 14

Membership and representing entities

1. The following entities may become Members of DiSSCo ERIC or may become Observers of DiSSCo ERIC without voting rights:
 - a) Member States of the European Union;
 - b) Associated countries;

- c) Third countries other than associated countries;
 - d) Intergovernmental organisations.
2. The membership of DiSSCo ERIC must include a Member State and two other countries that are either Member States or associated countries.
 3. Member States or associated countries shall hold jointly the majority of the voting rights in the General Assembly. The General Assembly shall determine any modification of voting rights that are necessary to ensure that DiSSCo ERIC complies at all times with this requirement.
 4. Any Member or an Observer referred to in paragraph (1)(a)-(c) may be represented by one or more public entities, including regions or a private entity with a public service mission, of its own choosing and appointed according to its own rules and procedures. Each Member or Observer shall inform the General Assembly of any change of its representing entity or entities, of the specific rights and obligations which have been delegated to it or of any other relevant change.
 5. The Members and the Observers as well as their representing entities are listed in Annex 1. Annex 1 shall be kept up to date by the Director General or any other person appointed by the Director General.

Article 15

Admission of Members and Observers

1. Entities referred to in Article 14(1), wishing to become Members of DiSSCo ERIC shall submit a written application to the Chairperson of the General Assembly. Such application shall describe how the entity will contribute to DiSSCo ERIC task described in Article 2 and how it will fulfil the obligations referred to in Article 18(2) and 18(3).
2. Entities referred to in Article 14(1) who wish to contribute to DiSSCo ERIC but are not yet in a position to join as Members may apply for an Observer status. Applicants shall submit a written application to the Chairperson of the General Assembly, which shall describe how the applicant will contribute to DiSSCo ERIC task described in Article 2 and how it will fulfil the obligations referred to in Article 19(2) and 19(3).
3. Where the General Assembly votes to admit an applicant as an Observer, it shall be limited for a two-year period. Observers may apply once for a two-year extension of their Observer status. In exceptional cases the General Assembly may accept and approve further extensions of an Observer status.

Article 16

Withdrawal and termination of a Membership or Observer status

1. A Member may withdraw its Membership at any time upon at least 12 months prior written notice to the Chairperson of the General Assembly. Withdrawal will come into effect after a minimum five-year period of Membership and at the end of the next financial year in which a

notice of withdrawal has been given, namely 31 December of the following year.

2. An Observer may withdraw at any time upon 6 months prior written notice to the Chairperson of the General Assembly. If notice is served by 30 June in any year, withdrawal will come into effect at the end of the same financial year in which notice has been given, namely 31 December. If notice is served after 30 June in any year, withdrawal will come into effect at the end of the next financial year in which notice has been given, namely 31 December of the following year.
3. The General Assembly may terminate Membership or an Observer status if any of the following conditions are met:
 - a) the Member or the Observer is in serious breach of one or more of its obligations or the conditions of Membership or Observer status under these Statutes, and
 - b) the Member or the Observer has failed to rectify such breach within a period of six months after it has received notice of the breach; and,
 - c) the Member or the Observer had been given an opportunity to present its position to the General Assembly before a decision is made.
4. Members [and Observers] shall continue paying their Membership [or Observer fees] and fulfil all other obligations to DiSSCo ERIC activities until withdrawal or termination comes into effect. They shall neither have the right to restitution or reimbursement of any contributions made, nor the right to lay any claim to the assets of DiSSCo ERIC.

Article 17

Strategic agreements

1. DiSSCo ERIC may enter into Strategic Agreements with third parties wishing to significantly contribute to the DiSSCo ERIC task described in Article 2 on a long-term basis.
2. Strategic Agreements may include, depending on the circumstances and assessed on a case-by-case basis, the grant of specific rights to a third party such as the right to attend the meetings of the General Assembly and to provide contributions in cash and/or in-kind.
3. Strategic Agreements shall be subject to approval by the General Assembly.
4. Additional procedures and conditions shall be set out in the Implementing Rules.

CHAPTER 4 - RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF MEMBERS AND OBSERVERS

Article 18

Members

1. Members shall have a right:
 - a) to attend and vote at the General Assembly, with the exception of voting on decisions regarding that Member's termination of Membership;

- b) for its research community to access the facilities, services and activities offered by DiSSCo, subject to DiSSCo ERIC Access Policy for Users;
 - c) to attend, elect and be elected to the governance bodies of DiSSCo ERIC through its representatives;
 - d) to host a National Node;
 - e) to any other benefit or right set out in the Implementing Rules.
2. A Member shall:
 - a) provide the annual Membership contribution in accordance with Annex 2;
 - b) appoint at least one, but not more than two, representatives to the General Assembly;
 - c) empower its representatives attending the General Assembly with full authority to vote on its behalf in all matters brought before the General Assembly .
 3. The General Assembly may decide to suspend a Member’s voting rights if that Member is 12 months or more in arrears of meeting its obligations under Article 18(2)(a), until contributions have been paid in full.
 4. A Member is also expected to support its National Node that it hosts to allow them to discharge their obligations as may be defined within a Service Level Agreement or a similar agreement with DiSSCo ERIC.

Article 19

Observers

1. Observers shall have a right:
 - a) To attend the meetings of the General Assembly, without voting rights;
 - b) For its research community to access the facilities, services and activities offered by DiSSCo, subject to DiSSCo ERIC Access Policy for Users;
 - c) To attend the meetings of the advisory committees of DiSSCo ERIC through its representatives, but without voting rights in such advisory committees;
 - d) To any other benefit or right set out in the Implementing Rules.
2. An Observer shall:
 - a) [Provide the annual Observer contribution in accordance with Annex 2];
 - b) Appoint at least one, but not more than two, representatives to the General Assembly;
 - c) Fulfil any other obligation negotiated between the respective Observer and DiSSCo ERIC as agreed by the General Assembly.

CHAPTER 5 - GOVERNANCE

Article 20

Bodies

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall comprise the following bodies:
 - a) The General Assembly
 - b) The Director General

- c) The Executive Board
- d) The Scientific, Ethical and Technical Advisory Committee
- e) The Nodes Advisory Committee

Article 21

The General Assembly

1. The General Assembly shall be the governing body of DiSSCo ERIC and shall be composed of representatives of the Members and Observers of DiSSCo ERIC. Each Member shall have a single indivisible vote with all votes being of equal value. Members abstaining from voting shall be counted as absent with no effect on the quorum required to constitute the meeting under paragraph .
2. Representatives to the General Assembly may be accompanied by up to two experts per delegation with the sole purpose of advising the delegation.
3. A member may be represented by another member, if notified to the Chairperson by the represented member prior to the meeting of the General Assembly. A Member may not represent more than one Member in each meeting.
4. The Director General, and the Chairs of the advisory Committees shall attend the meetings of the General Assembly, unless otherwise directed by the Chair of the General Assembly. Additional guests may be invited by the Chairperson of the General Assembly.
5. The General Assembly shall elect a Chairperson and a Vice-Chairperson amongst the representatives of the Members for a two-year term, renewable for the same period, twice. The Vice-Chairperson shall substitute the Chairperson in his/her absence, resignation, inability to act or in cases of conflict of interest which cannot be otherwise resolved. With their elections the Chairperson and, when acting as a substitute, the Vice-Chairperson, become *supra-parte* and leave their delegations. The Member from which the Chairperson or, if applicable, the Vice-Chairperson originates shall have the right to nominate another representative instead.
6. The General Assembly shall be convened by the Chairperson at least once per calendar year and shall be responsible for the overall direction and supervision of DiSSCo ERIC.
7. A meeting shall be quorate if at least two thirds of the Members are represented at the meeting. If the required quorum is not met, the Chairperson shall convene another meeting, following a new invitation with the same agenda, not sooner than 14 days later. The second meeting shall be quorate if at least 50% of the Members are represented at the meeting. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the Chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the 50% of Members are present or represented.
8. The General Assembly shall strive to reach decisions by consensus. If consensus cannot be reached, decisions shall be taken by vote of the Members.

9. The following matters shall require approval of the General Assembly by unanimous vote of the Members represented:
 - a) Amendment of the Statutes of DiSSCo ERIC;
 - b) Winding up of DiSSCo ERIC in accordance with Article 3;
 - c) Termination of a Membership or Observer status.

10. The following matters shall require approval of the General Assembly by a two thirds majority of the votes of the Members represented:
 - a) Setting or changing the level of annual Membership and Observer contribution;
 - b) Approval of the annual budget and annual accounts;
 - c) Approval of the annual activity report;
 - d) Approval of the annual work plan;
 - e) Approval of a five years strategy and financial plans;
 - f) Adoption or amendment of the Implementing Rules;
 - g) Election of a Chairperson and a Vice-Chairperson from among the Members following nominations;
 - h) Appointment and dismissal of the Director General;
 - i) Appointment and dismissal of representatives to the advisory committees listed in Article 20(1)(c)-(e);
 - j) Acceptance of new Members and Observers or renewal of an Observer status;
 - k) Adoption of a Strategic Agreement with a third party referred to in Article 17.
 - l) Establishment and elimination of advisory committees;

11. All other decisions of the General Assembly shall require a simple majority of the votes of the Members represented.

12. Subject to these Statutes, the General Assembly shall adopt its own rules of procedure in the Implementing Rules, setting out detailed rules and procedures for the work of the General Assembly, including the possibility to conduct meetings virtually (by video, telephone, or other electronic means), extraordinary meetings, and the possibility to adopt decisions by a written procedure.

Article 22

Director General

1. The General Assembly shall appoint the Director General of DiSSCo ERIC, who shall be the legal representative of DiSSCo ERIC.
2. The Director General shall be employed by DiSSCo ERIC.
3. The Director General shall:
 - a) Carry out the day-to-day management of DiSSCo ERIC;
 - b) Implement the decisions of the General Assembly in accordance with applicable law and regulations;
 - c) Consult and seek advice from the Executive Board on matters related to the operation of

- DiSSCo;
- d) Submit an annual activity report to the General Assembly after consultation with the Nodes Advisory Committee;
 - e) Submit an annual report to the European Commission;
 - f) Appoint, dismiss and manage the staff of the DiSSCo ERIC;
 - g) Prepare the DiSSCo work and financial plan for approval by the General Assembly;
 - h) Represent DiSSCo at national and international fora and actively contribute to the community building and fostering external relations and strategic partnerships;
 - i) Carry out any other relevant task as may be required by the General Assembly.
4. The term for the Director General appointment shall be five years. The General Assembly may renew the term once for an additional period of up to five years.
 5. The General Assembly may adopt additional terms of reference for the Director General in the Implementing Rules.

Article 23

Executive Board

1. The Executive Board shall be composed of no less than three and no more than five individuals, nominated by the Nodes Advisory Committee and appointed by the General Assembly. The Executive Board shall be chaired by the Director General.
2. The Executive Board shall:
 - a) Assist the Director General in the implementation of the decisions by the General Assembly in accordance with these Statutes, the Implementing Rules and applicable law;
 - b) Assist the Director General in the implementation of DiSSCo strategic work programmes;
 - c) Help to implement the recommendations of the Nodes Advisory Committee within the framework of the DiSSCo ERIC tasks and the instructions of the Director General;
 - d) Represent DiSSCo at national and international fora;
 - e) Contribute to and facilitate constructive communication and harmonised implementation of the DiSSCo Work programmes with the National Nodes.
3. The General Assembly may adopt additional terms of reference for the Executive Board in the Implementing Rules.

Article 24

Scientific, Ethical and Technical Advisory Committee

1. The General Assembly shall establish an independent Scientific, Ethical, and Technical Advisory Committee, whose representatives shall be appointed by the General Assembly on a

worldwide basis, without a requirement to be based in a Member or Observer country.

2. The Scientific, Ethical and Technical Advisory Committee shall report to the General Assembly.
3. The Director General may request advice from the Scientific, Ethical and Technical Advisory Committee on various matters within their competence.
4. The Scientific, Ethical and Technical Advisory Committee shall:
 - a) Evaluate the scientific, technical, and ethical activities of DiSSCo ERIC and report to the General Assembly on an annual basis;
 - b) Provide feedback and make recommendations on actions to improve the effectiveness of DiSSCo outcomes in the scientific community with a view to further develop DiSSCo ERIC's scientific, technical and ethical activities;
5. The rules of procedure for the Scientific, Ethical and Technical Advisory Committee shall be approved by the General Assembly and set out in the Implementing Rules.

Article 25

Nodes Advisory Committee

1. The General Assembly shall establish a Nodes Advisory Committee that will be composed of the Representing Organisation of the National Nodes (RONNs) and the DiSSCo Service Provider Nodes (SPNs).
2. The Nodes Advisory Committee shall advise the Director General.
3. The Nodes Advisory Committee shall:
 - a) Collect and consolidate the views of the RONNs and the SPNs with a view to formulating relevant recommendations;
 - b) Ensure alignment of the policies implemented in the DiSSCo distributed research infrastructure;
 - c) Ensure consistency and coherency of the activities carried out at the DiSSCo distributed research infrastructure;
 - d) Advise on national priorities and trends;
 - e) Advise on User needs and new User communities at national level.
4. The rules of procedure for the Nodes Advisory Committee shall be approved by the General Assembly and set out in the Implementing Rules.

CHAPTER 6 – FINANCIAL MATTERS

Article 26

Contributions and resources

1. Annual cash contributions shall be paid by Members [and Observers] in accordance with the principles set out in Annex 2.
2. The resources of DiSSCo ERIC may also include the following:
 - a) Research and other grants;
 - b) In-kind contributions;
 - c) Subject to Article 2(4), income derived from limited economic activities;
 - d) Contributions other than the annual cash contributions referred to in paragraph 1.
 - e) Other resources, including donations and gifts, within limits and under terms and conditions approved by the General Assembly, in compliance with applicable law and regulations.
3. DiSSCo ERIC contributions and resources shall be used for pursuing the task and activities set out in Article 2 of these Statutes.

Article 27

Budgetary principles, accounts and audit

1. The financial year of DiSSCo ERIC shall be a Calendar Year.
2. DiSSCo ERIC shall operate within the principles of transparency and sound financial management and be subject to the requirements of the applicable law of the country where it has its statutory seat as regards to preparation, filing, auditing and publication of accounts.
3. The accounts of DiSSCo ERIC shall be accompanied by a report on budgetary and financial management of the financial year.
4. DiSSCo ERIC shall record the costs and revenues of any economic activities separately.
5. DiSSCo ERIC may adopt financial rules, approved by the General Assembly and set out in the Implementing Rules.

Article 28

Tax and excise duty exemption

1. Value Added Tax (VAT) exemptions based on Article 143(1) (g) and Article 151(1)(b) of Directive 2006/112/EC and in accordance with Articles 50 and 51 of Council Implementing Regulation (EU) No 282/2011 shall be applied to purchases by DiSSCo ERIC and by Members of DiSSCo ERIC which are for the official and exclusive use by DiSSCo ERIC, provided that such purchases are made solely for the non-economic activities of DiSSCo ERIC in line with its activities. VAT exemptions shall be limited to purchases exceeding the value of EUR 300.
2. Excise duty exemptions based on Article 11 of Council Directive 2020/1262 shall be limited to purchases by DiSSCo ERIC which are for the official and exclusive use by DiSSCo ERIC, provided that such purchases are made solely for the non-economic activities of DiSSCo ERIC in line with its activities and that each purchase exceed the value of EUR 300. Purchases by staff members are not covered by the exemption.

CHAPTER 7 – FINAL PROVISIONS

Article 29

Data policy

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall promote open source, open access and FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) principles.
2. DiSSCo ERIC shall provide guidance to Users to ensure that research involving material made accessible through DiSSCo ERIC shall be undertaken within a framework that recognizes the rights of data owners and privacy of individuals.
3. DiSSCo ERIC shall ensure that Users agree to the terms and conditions governing access and that suitable security arrangements are in place regarding storage and handling of data.
4. DiSSCo ERIC shall ensure that the data providers, right holders, authors and DiSSCo ERIC are acknowledged in an appropriate manner.
5. DiSSCo ERIC shall adopt a data policy, for approval by the General Assembly.

Article 30

Reporting to the Commission

1. DiSSCo ERIC shall produce an annual activity report, containing in particular the scientific, operational and financial aspects of its activities. The report shall be drafted by the Director General and approved by the General Assembly and submitted to the Commission within six months from the end of the corresponding financial year. After approval by the General Assembly the report shall be made publicly available through the DiSSCo ERIC website.
2. DiSSCo ERIC shall inform the Commission of any circumstances which threaten to seriously jeopardise the achievement of DiSSCo ERIC tasks or hinder DiSSCo ERIC from fulfilling the requirements laid down in Regulation (EC) No 723/2009.

Article 31

Implementing Rules

These Statutes shall be supplemented by Implementing Rules to be adopted by the General Assembly.

Article 32

Applicable law

DiSSCo ERIC shall be governed by:

- a) European Union law, in particular Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 and the decisions referred to in Article 6(1)(a) and 11(1) of the regulation;
- b) [INSERT COUNTRY] law in the case of matters not, or only partly, regulated by European Union law;
- c) these Statutes, and their Implementing Rules.

Article 33

Disputes

1. The Members shall, as far as possible, try to settle by amicable means (including mediation) any disputes which may arise from interpretation or application of these Statutes or the Implementing Rules.
2. The Court of Justice of the European Union shall have jurisdiction over litigation among the Members in relation to DiSSCo ERIC, between Members and the DiSSCo ERIC and over any litigation to which the Union is a party.
3. Union legislation on jurisdiction shall apply to disputes between DiSSCo ERIC and third parties. In cases not covered by Union legislation, the law of [INSERT COUNTRY] shall determine the competent jurisdiction for the resolution of such disputes.

Article 34

Setting-up provisions

1. A constitutional meeting of the General Assembly shall be called by [INSERT COUNTRY] as soon as possible, and no later than 90 days after the Commission Decision setting up DiSSCo ERIC takes effect.
2. Before the constitutional meeting of the General Assembly is held, [INSERT COUNTRY] shall notify the Members and Observers of any specific urgent legal action that needs to be taken on behalf of DiSSCo ERIC. Unless a Member objects within five working days after being notified, the legal action shall be carried out by a person duly authorised by [INSERT COUNTRY].

Annex 1. The Members and Observers and their current representing entities

This annex lists the Members and the Observers, and the entities representing them. [to be added]

Annex 2. Annual contributions

[to be added]